

Autocatalytic properties of biochar during lignocellulose pyrolysis probed using a continuous reaction system

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Abstract

The autocatalytic role of the biochar formed during the pyrolysis of oak woodchips has been in situ assessed using a continuous reaction system. To that end, the evolution of the product distribution along the time on stream was evaluated at different temperatures ranging between 300 and 550 °C. When working at low temperatures (300 and 350 °C), the system operates under almost steady state conditions with little variations in the yield and composition of the pyrolysis fractions. However, at higher temperatures, a progressive reduction in the bio-oil* yield (bio-oil on a water-free basis) is observed along the time on stream, which is accompanied by a significant increase in the gas production, mainly as a result of the enhanced generation of CO and CO₂. Within the liquid organic fraction, these transformations cause a gradual reduction in its oxygen content and affect to a greater extent the heavy/oligomeric components. Likewise, noticeable variations are denoted along the time on stream for other bio-oil* components, such as carboxylic acids, sugars, and oxygenated aromatics. Additional pyrolysis tests, performed using two biochars with different K content as external catalysts, confirm that the origin of the biochar catalytic effects can be linked with its relatively high AAEMs (alkali and alkaline earth metals) content. Nevertheless, the contribution of the biochar carbonaceous matter should be also taken into account since it may retain many of the species present in the pyrolysis vapours, in particular the heaviest components, thus facilitating their subsequent conversion.

Keywords

Lignocellulose, pyrolysis, biochar, autocatalytic, continuous reactor

1. Introduction

Lignocellulosic biomass is one of the most promising alternatives to mitigate the environmental impacts derived from the over-exploitation of fossil fuels since it is an abundant, renewable and low-cost resource. Thus, lignocellulosic biomass can be used as a feedstock to produce not only biofuels but also high-added value platform molecules such as furfural, γ -valerolactone, phenolics, or levoglucosan, which are considered potential precursors of a wide spectrum of chemicals typically obtained from petroleum [1–4]. However, lignocellulose conversion still faces several challenges related to its recalcitrant and complex structure, having a composition that strongly depends on the type of plant as well as on the location and climate of the place of origin [5].

In recent years, the scientific community has been focused on developing efficient and sustainable processes to transform lignocellulose into valuable biomass-derived compounds. Among them, biomass pyrolysis is considered one of the most feasible technologies due to its simplicity, short operation times and versatility to admit a wide range of waste materials as feedstock [6,7]. This thermochemical process consists of the thermal decomposition of lignocellulose under inert atmosphere at temperatures in the range of 400-700 °C yielding three products: a liquid bio-oil, a solid biochar, and a non-condensable gaseous fraction mainly constituted by CO, CO₂, H₂, and hydrocarbons from C₁ to C₄ [8].

Although pyrolysis has been traditionally applied for the production of biochar, which can be used as a solid fuel or soil amendment material, in recent decades a great interest has arisen in the possible use of bio-oil as a source of both liquid fuels and bio-based chemicals [9]. However, as a consequence of their high oxygen and water contents, pyrolysis bio-oils exhibit high acidity and viscosity, instability during storage, and low HHV, which limits their use as low-quality fuel in turbines and boilers [10]. Bio-oil properties can be considerably improved by the incorporation of catalysts during the pyrolysis process due to the promotion of a wide variety of

reactions, such as cracking, decarboxylation, decarbonylation, and condensation reactions, enhancing their properties as fuels or addressing the selectivity towards high-value products, such as aromatics, and phenols [11].

A large variety of catalysts, including metal oxides (Al_2O_3 , CeO_2 , CaO) [6,12], inorganic salts (Na_2CO_3 , K_2CO_3) [13], zeolites [14], mesostructured aluminosilicates [15], and activated carbons, have been widely investigated for biomass catalytic pyrolysis [16]. In particular, activated carbons, which are usually obtained via physical or chemical activation of organic precursors such as pyrolysis biochars, have been extensively applied for the production of pyrolysis bio-oils rich in phenolic compounds of industrial interest [6,13,17].

In addition, the biochar itself exhibits properties that make it attractive to be used as catalyst in the own pyrolysis process, such as a relatively developed porous structure and a highly functionalized surface rich in hydroxyl, carbonyl, carboxylic and aromatic groups, metallic species, etc. [18,19]. Hence, the evaluation of the catalytic properties of the biochar during the pyrolysis of lignocellulose is of great interest not only in terms of sustainability and cost-effectiveness of the process but also to establish how it influences the bio-oil yield and composition. However, just a few works can be found covering the catalytic behaviour of biochars in the pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass. Thus, Qui *et al.* tested a variety of biochars, prepared from the pyrolysis of different mixtures of sewage sludge and rice husk, in the co-pyrolysis of the same feedstock [20], which led to the production of a bio-oil with an augmented HHV. In the same way, Wang *et al.* evaluated the catalytic effect of a nanocellulose biochar on the pyrolysis of Douglas fir obtaining an enhanced selectivity towards phenolic monomers [21]. Similarly, Dong and co-workers reported the improved production of acetic acid and phenol during the pyrolysis of bamboo sawdust using the biochar obtained from this biomass as catalyst [22]. However, in these works, the biochars are recovered from the reaction system and then

used as catalyst in a different pyrolysis test, which may cause important changes in their properties and, therefore, in their catalytic behaviour during cooling, storage and heating steps.

Considering all these aspects, the current work investigates the autocatalytic activity of the biochar from oak tree biomass under in situ conditions using a continuous flow reactor in which this product is progressively accumulated forming a fixed bed on the upper part of the reaction system. Accordingly, and based on the changes in the product distribution and composition along the time on stream, it has been possible to elucidate the autocatalytic properties of the biochar and how they depend on the pyrolysis temperature. In this context, it is shown that the autocatalytic effect of the biochar may induce sharp changes in the bio-oil yield and composition. Moreover, further insights on the catalytic role of both carbonaceous matter and AAEMs present in the biochar have been derived from catalytic pyrolysis tests using two biochar samples as external catalysts.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Biomass feedstock characterization

The feedstock used in this study was oak tree biomass (*Quercus Robur*) from forestry residues, which was supplied in the form of woodchips with no bark by Ence, Spain. It was grounded in a cutting mill and sieved to a particle size of 0.5-1 mm, then being oven-dried at 90 °C for 48 h before analysis and pyrolysis experiments.

Biomass proximate analysis was performed following the European standards procedures UNE-EN ISO 18134-1:2016, UNE-EN ISO 18122:2016, and UNE-EN ISO 18123:2016 to determine the moisture, ash, and volatile matter contents, respectively. Moisture content was estimated by weighting the biomass after drying at 105 °C in an oven for 12 h. Volatile matter content was calculated by TGA analysis (Netzsch, STA 449 F3 with SiC oven), heating the sample up to 900 °C with a rate of 10 °C/min, while ash content was obtained by calcination in a muffle oven at 550 °C for 30 min under static air conditions. Fixed carbon was calculated by difference.

Ash composition was determined using ICP-OES equipment (Perkin-Elmer, Optima 7300 DV), after acid digesting the ash samples under microwave heat radiation. Silica content was calculated by difference [23–25]. Elemental C, H, N, S analysis was performed using an elemental analyser (Thermo Scientific, Flash 2000), oxygen content being determined by difference. Proximate and ultimate analyses, as well as the ash composition of the biomass feedstock, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Proximate and ultimate analyses, and ash composition of grounded oak woodchips.

Proximate analysis (wt%)								
Moisture	Volatile matter			Fixed carbon			Ash	
2.4	79.7			16.1			1.8	
Ultimate analysis (wt%)								
C	H	N	S	O				
49.9	6.0	0.1	0.0	44.00				
Ash composition (mg/kg _{biomass})								
Al	Ca	Fe	K	Mg	Mn	Na	P	Si
1.8	1414	1.8	1223	19.3	12.3	7.0	10.5	14810

2.2. Continuous pyrolysis set-up

The continuous pyrolysis experiments were carried out in a stainless-steel downdraft reactor (21 mm i.d., 600 mm length), as shown in Figure 1. The set-up was designed to run both thermal and catalytic pyrolysis. In the tests performed without any external catalyst, the lower section was left empty. However, in the experiments carried out using biochar as an external catalyst, the lower zone incorporated a catalytic bed from the beginning of the test. To that end, two biochar samples were employed: the biochar produced in the test at 500 °C and this material after potassium impregnation. For the preparation of this second sample, the biochar was loaded with 5 wt% of K by means of wet impregnation using KNO₃ and demineralized water (5 ml/g_{biochar}). The sample was left under stirring at 60 °C for 1 h. Then, it was dried in a rotary evaporator and pretreated at 500 °C for 2 h under inert atmosphere. The material so obtained was named *biochar-K* while the non-impregnated one was denoted *biochar-raw*.

Oak wood particles were fed through a screw pump built upon commission by PID Eng&Tech, Spain, while 100 ml/min of N₂ were used as both purge and sweep gas that was fed employing two mass flow controllers (Bronkhorst, El-Flow). The reactor is divided into two zones (upper and lower), heated independently by two electric furnaces, the internal temperature of the reactor being monitored using two K-type thermocouples, one for each zone. Stainless steel tubes, nets, and quartz wool were used as fillers to achieve the double bed in the reactor.

Biomass feeding started after the reactor was purged and the desired temperature was reached, with a fixed rate of 5 g/h. Biochar and pyrolysis vapors were generated in the upper pyrolysis zone, so biochar was accumulated in this section as more biomass was fed and pyrolyzed. The condensable fraction of the pyrolysis product (bio-oil) was collected in a series of 4 glass condensers of 250 ml, which were soaked in an ice bath. The non-condensable gases were collected in gas sampling bags, quantifying their flow rate using a volumetric gas meter (Ritter, TG0.5/5).

Different thermal pyrolysis experiments were carried out by changing the temperature of the reactor upper zone (300, 350, 400, 450, 500, and 550 °C), to investigate how this parameter affects product yields and composition. The reactor lower zone temperature was fixed at 450 °C for the experiments performed in the absence of external catalysts, whereas the pressure of the system was kept at atmospheric. In order to study how the continuous pyrolysis set-up behaves over time, each experiment had a duration of 4 h, with bio-oil and gas sampling being performed at intervals of 1 h and 20 min, respectively. The results were expressed as hourly values, which correspond with average times on stream of 0.5, 1.5, 2.5, and 3.5 h, respectively. In the case of the tests carried out using biochars as external catalysts, the temperature of the catalytic bed in the lower zone of the reaction system was set at 500 °C.

This type of reaction system has been designed and built mainly for research purposes since it allows the in situ assessment of the catalytic properties of biochar. Nevertheless, it could be also

employed at larger scale provided that the biochar is accumulated in a space at a lower temperature to avoid its catalytic interference on the reaction system. With this experimental setup, it is also possible to establish the behaviour of the system when the biochar accumulation is negligible by extrapolating the product distribution data at zero time on stream.

Figure 1. Scheme of the continuous pyrolysis reaction system.

2.3. Product characterization and data evaluation

Biochar was recovered from the reactor upper zone after each experiment, then it was characterized according to the same analytical techniques and procedures used for the bio-oil and raw biomass characterization (elemental analysis, ash composition). Moreover, Raman Spectroscopy of biochars was also performed to determine their amorphous carbon structure using NRS-5100 JASCO spectrometer (excitation laser wavelength = 532 nm). Based on previous works [26,27], the original Raman spectra were curve-fitted into ten Gaussian bands. Briefly, the ratio between D band area and ($G_R + V_L + V_R$) band area indicates the relationship between the

large and the small fused-aromatic units (< 6 and > 6 rings) present in amorphous carbon in biochars. Likewise, the presence of functional groups on the biochar surface was checked by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) using a Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700 spectrometer, equipped with a diamond accessory for attenuated total reflectance (ATR), in the wavenumber range of 4000 - 800 cm^{-1} .

Gaseous products composition was measured using a micro-GC analyser (Agilent Technologies, 490) equipped with a molecular sieve (Molsieve 5 Å), PPQ columns, and a thermal conductivity detector (TDC). The quantified gaseous components were H_2 , CO , CO_2 , CH_4 , C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , C_3H_6 , C_3H_8 , C_4H_8 , and C_4H_{10} .

In some experiments (500 and 550 °C), the bio-oil consisted of two phases (aqueous and organic) that were separated by centrifugation, weighted, and analysed separately. The results presented in this work include the weighted sum of the two phases to be compared with single-phase bio-oils. Bio-oil water content was determined using a Karl-Fischer titration instrument (Mettler-Toledo, V20), so the bio-oil yield and characterization results were calculated on a water-free basis, referring to it as bio-oil* and considering water as a fourth fraction of the pyrolysis reaction. The bio-oil* chemical composition was analysed using a gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (Agilent 8860 GC-5977B GC/MSD equipped with a fused silica HP5-MS UI column 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 mm), and the NIST 2017 spectral library for the identification of compounds with a minimum matching factor of 85/100 (typically over 90/100). The main components were calibrated by means of the internal standard calibration method to estimate their mass concentration from the respective response factor using cyclohexanol as an internal standard. Before the analysis, the bio-oil samples were diluted 1:10 with a solution of dioxane. All compounds were grouped into different families depending on their main functional groups. An average response factor of each family was calculated from the calibrated molecules to be applied to the minority compounds (those with a relative area in the GC/MS chromatogram less

than 1%) that belonged to the same family. The following families were considered for this study: carboxylic acids (AC), ketones and ethers (KET & ETH), furans (FUR), oxygenated aromatics (O-AR), and sugars (SUG). The sum of the mass concentration of all compounds indicates the percentage of bio-oil* that was detected and quantified by the GC-MS analysis. This percentage was denoted as bio-oil* total GC-MS detected fraction, and it was used to estimate the share of light compounds in the bio-oil* with respect to the heavier ones, which were not visible by this technique.

Additionally, the overall mass balance was assessed from the total weight of the products collected at the end of the tests. In all cases, the experimental error was lower than 5 % regarding the total amount of biomass fed along the time on stream Eq.1). Likewise, hourly mass balances were evaluated considering the theoretical biomass fed during the corresponding reaction time to avoid errors due to possible oscillations in its flow rate. The same equations can be used to calculate both total and hourly yields of every compound family detected in the bio-oil* by GC-MS analysis, and the yields of non-condensable gases detected by micro-GC analysis.

$$Mass\ yield_{i,h}[wt.\%/h] = \frac{Mass_{i,h}[g]}{Total\ biomass_h[g]} \cdot 100 \quad Eq.1$$

Where i = gas, biochar, bio-oil* and water, and h = reaction time when the sample was collected.

3. Results and discussion

The pyrolysis tests of oak wood have been performed using a continuous reaction system operating at different temperatures (300, 350, 400, 450, 500, and 550 °C) with a total duration of 4 h. In this continuous pyrolysis system, interactions between vapours generated in biomass pyrolysis and biochar can be elucidated by investigating how they are affected by two critical operational parameters: time on stream and pyrolysis temperature.

3.1. Pyrolysis products distribution

Hourly yields of the main pyrolysis products (bio-oil*, gas and water) are shown in Figure 2-a, b, and c, respectively. These tests have been performed in a continuous reactor in the absence of any external catalyst. Accordingly, the system should operate under steady-state conditions, i.e. with no changes in the yield and composition of the products along the time on stream. This is what occurs when performing the pyrolysis at relatively low temperatures (300 and 350 °C), the curves showing the expected trend with little variations along the time on stream. However, when increasing the temperature of the zone in which the biochar is accumulated, the yield of the different fractions and components, as well as the composition of the gaseous and bio-oil fractions, undergo remarkable changes along the time on stream. In particular, the bio-oil* yield is progressively reduced and the gaseous fraction is enhanced. Interestingly, the variations in the bio-oil* and gas production along the reaction time are more pronounced as the pyrolysis temperature rises. Thus, at 550 °C the bio-oil* yield decreases from 42.8 to 23.2 wt% in 4 h, while at 300 °C is kept practically constant at about 32 wt%.

This apparently anomalous behaviour, occurring for temperatures ≥ 400 °C, is a clear indication that the biochar bed, which is progressively built during the test in the upper zone of the reaction system, possesses catalytic properties, hence the system no longer operates in steady-state conditions. In this way, a progressive rise in the space time, defined as the mass or volume of catalyst (biochar) referred to the biomass feeding rate, occurs along the time on stream. These effects are more pronounced when rising the pyrolysis temperature as it enhances the biochar catalytic activity, thus increasing the variations observed along the time on stream.

Figure 2. Yields of bio-oil* (a), gas (b) and water (c) as a function of time on stream and pyrolysis temperature.

Figure 3 displays the cumulative yields of the different fractions corresponding to the whole duration of the pyrolysis tests. Biochar is generated from the primary decomposition of lignocellulose biopolymers, and by secondary carbonization of pyrolysis vapours to a minor extent [28]. Its yield is reduced when increasing the pyrolysis temperature since the decomposition of biopolymers is favoured, and more vapours and gases are generated.

Gas production increases continuously with the temperature as secondary cracking and deoxygenation reactions of vapours become predominant, generating light gases to the detriment of both the condensable fraction and the biochar [29]. The production of gases is boosted at 500 and 550 °C, as well as at long reaction times, denoting the important catalytic role of biochar in promoting those reactions. In particular, the increased formation of gases could be attributed to the presence of AAEMs (alkali and alkaline earth metals) species in the biomass, especially Ca and K, which are concentrated in the biochar fraction when the biopolymers are decomposed. These metals are catalytically active even at very low concentrations and they can promote a variety of secondary reactions, reducing the bio-oil* production (cracking, deoxygenation) and favouring secondary biochar formation (carbonization, condensation, oligomerization) [30–35].

The bio-oil* yield presents a maximum of 39.4 wt% at 450 °C, where an optimum between biomass devolatilization and secondary cracking of vapours is reached. The reduction of the bio-oil* yield between 450 and 550 °C is more significant if compared to the decrease of the biochar yield, indicating that in this temperature range the gases were generated mainly at the expense of the bio-oil*. On the other hand, the overall water yield is practically constant for all the investigated temperatures with a value of ca. 15 – 16 wt%. However, since water is collected in the liquid phase together with the organic bio-oil*, the total liquid product obtained at 550 °C has a higher water content than the one obtained at 450 °C. In fact, for the pyrolysis tests at 500 and 550 °C, the water content of bio-oil was high enough to provoke a phase separation. In the pyrolysis of dry biomass, water is mainly generated from dehydration reactions, which have been proposed to be catalysed also by the minerals present in the biochar [36,37]. However, in the tests here reported the water production seems to be little affected neither by the temperature nor the reaction time, which can be assigned to a prompt consumption of most of the water released from dehydration reactions.

Figure 3. Cumulative yields of the pyrolysis products as a function of pyrolysis temperature.

3.2. Gas yield and composition

Figure 4 depicts the evolution over time of the yields corresponding to the different components (CO_2 , CO, light paraffins, and olefins) detected in the gas stream. It can be observed that they follow the same trend of the overall gas product (Figure 2-b), with an increase that is more pronounced at higher temperatures (500-550 °C). These results indicate that the biochar catalyses both cracking and deoxygenation reactions via decarboxylation and decarbonylation. In this way, the CO/ CO_2 molar ratio increases with temperature, but it is quite stable along the time on stream (Figure S1). This finding denotes that the biochar favours the production of both CO and CO_2 in a similar extension, while the increase of the temperature shifts the selectivity of the deoxygenation pathways towards decarbonylation [37,38].

Figure 4. Yields of the gaseous components as a function of time on stream and pyrolysis temperature: CO₂ (a), CO (b), light paraffins (LP) (c) and light olefins (LO) (d).

The cumulative yield of the gaseous components is shown in Figure 5-a as a function of the pyrolysis temperature. In agreement with the previous discussion of the evolution of temporal profiles, CO₂ and CO are by far the main components of the gas stream. Their yields are particularly enhanced at temperatures of 500 and 550 °C, which can be linked to the increased activity of AAEMs species and their ability to catalyse deoxygenation reactions. The cumulative yield of CO is quite more influenced by the temperature increase than that of CO₂. Thus, the CO/CO₂ molar ratio varies from 0.87 to 1.72 when the temperature is risen from 300 to 550 °C, as shown in Figure 5-b. This fact confirms that the temperature strongly modifies the overall deoxygenation selectivity in favour of decarbonylation.

Figure 5. Cumulative yields of CO₂, CO, H₂, light paraffins (LP) and light olefins (LO) (a) and molar ratio CO to CO₂ (b) as a function of pyrolysis temperature.

3.3. Bio-oil and biochar elemental composition

Bio-oil and biochar were characterized in terms of elemental composition, which is reported as cumulative values (for the whole duration of the pyrolysis experiments) in Table 2. As expected, the elemental composition of the biochars is quite different in comparison with those of the corresponding bio-oils*. In general, biochars are more concentrated in carbon and present considerably fewer contents of the other elements (H, N, and O).

Interestingly, both bio-oil* and biochar undergo some common changes in the C and O shares with the pyrolysis temperature. Thus, the carbon content of both bio-oil* and biochar is further increased at the expense of the reduction in the oxygen one, as a consequence of the great extension of decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions when augmenting the pyrolysis temperature. Nevertheless, the reduction in the oxygen content is much more pronounced for the solid fraction: it decreases from ~40 to ~30 wt% in the range 300 - 550 °C for the bio-oil*, while it decreases from ~21 to ~8 wt% for the biochar. Taking into account the oxygen content

of the raw biomass (44 wt%, see Table 1), it can be concluded that the bio-oil* undergoes little deoxygenation at lower temperatures (between 300 and 400 °C), which means that the observed deoxygenation selectivity (with a prevalence of decarboxylation against decarbonylation) corresponds mainly with the biochar formation. A noticeable fact is that the biochar elemental composition does not almost change when the temperature is increased from 300 to 400 °C, but it is sharply modified in the temperature range of 400 - 500 °C (Table 2), rising its C content while those of H, N, and O are significantly reduced. Interestingly, this last interval corresponds with the first detection of catalytic effects of the biochar, as above reported when discussing the time evolution of pyrolysis products.

To gain more information about the changes undergone by the carbonaceous matter, the biochar samples produced at 400 and 500 °C have been characterized by FTIR and Raman spectroscopy, as shown in Figures S2 and S3, respectively. The FTIR spectra illustrate how the intensity of the peaks corresponding to different oxygenated functional groups decreases significantly when the pyrolysis temperature is increased. Thus, the band assigned to -COOH groups (1700 cm^{-1}) disappears completely in the biochar produced at 500 °C, whereas the bands associated with C-O and O-H (1430 and 1200 cm^{-1} , respectively) become less intense. Similarly, the band at 1600 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the stretching of different functionalities (C=C, C=O, and C-C) [39–41], is lower intense for the biochar obtained at 500 °C, suggesting a reduction in the concentration of C=O groups. On the other hand, from the Raman spectra, the ratio between amorphous (D band, 1350 cm^{-1}) and graphitic (G band, 1600 cm^{-1}) carbon structure can be calculated by obtaining the following values: 0.56 and 0.88 for the biochars derived from the tests performed at pyrolysis temperatures of 400 and 500 °C, respectively. These results denote that the share of amorphous carbon increases significantly with the pyrolysis temperature, in good agreement with previous literature [42]. Additionally, the ratio between small and large aromatic ring systems ($I_{\text{GR+VL+VR}}/I_{\text{D}}$) can be also deduced from the deconvoluted Raman spectra. This ratio is reduced at higher pyrolysis temperatures, varying from 1.76 to 1.28 for the tests

performed at 400 and 500 °C, respectively, which are congruent with data reported by Huang *et al.* [43]. Therefore, it can be concluded that the biochar nature depends strongly on the pyrolysis temperature, evolving towards a low functionalized and highly condensed amorphous carbonaceous matter. Accordingly, the autocatalytic behaviour of biochar may be influenced by the nature of the carbon structure and not just by its high AAEMs content.

Table 2. Bio-oil and biochar elemental composition as a function of pyrolysis temperature.*

T (°C)	Bio-oil* (wt. %)				Biochar (wt. %)			
	C	H	N	O	C	H	N	O
300	52.6	6.6	0.6	40.2	74.5	3.8	0.4	21.4
350	54.2	6.5	0.8	38.5	76.6	3.5	0.3	19.6
400	55.0	6.9	0.4	37.7	75.0	3.1	0.4	21.5
450	58.7	6.6	0.6	34.1	82.8	3.1	0.3	13.8
500	61.0	6.8	0.6	31.6	88.8	2.9	0.2	8.1
550	61.5	7.6	1.6	29.3	88.8	2.5	0.2	8.5

A low oxygen content is a desired feature in the bio-oil* for energy applications, since the presence of oxygenated species reduces its HHV. However, deoxygenation by decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions also removes large amounts of carbon, lowering the bio-oil* yield, and being a process that needs further optimization despite many studies have been already carried out [44–47]. In this way, Figure 6 depicts the time evolution of bio-oil* oxygen content, showing that it is relatively constant when operating in the range of 300 – 450 °C, but starts decreasing with the time on stream for the tests performed above those temperatures. This effect is more pronounced when increasing the pyrolysis temperature, reaching an oxygen content of ca. 20 wt% for the sample obtained at 550 °C at the longest reaction time, which is obtained at the expense of reducing the yield of this liquid fraction to ca. 32 wt%. Therefore, these values evidence that biochar plays also a major role in the bio-oil* deoxygenation process.

Figure 6. Bio-oil* oxygen content as a function of the time on stream and pyrolysis temperature.

3.4. Bio-oil molecular composition

Bio-oil* molecular composition is important to assess the quality and possible applications of this fraction, either as fuel or for the production of bio-based chemicals. Hence, Figure 7 shows the temporal profiles of the yields corresponding to the different organic compound families detected by GC-MS at three different temperatures: 300, 450 and 550 °C.

According to the time evolution of the total bio-oil* and gas yields at the lowest temperature (300 °C), which have been discussed above, it should be expected to observe just slight differences in the tendencies of each family at this temperature. This assumption can be confirmed by checking Figure 7-a, where there are no significant changes in the production of sugars, furans, acids, ketones, and ethers, or oxygenated aromatics along the time on stream for the lowest pyrolysis temperature. The same occurs for the overall yields of both GC-MS detected and non-detected components, as shown in Figure 8. However, this is not the case at

the two other temperatures because of the effects derived from the catalytic properties of biochar. Thus, for both 450 and 550 °C, it can be observed that the already commented reduction in the total bio-oil* yield (see Figure 2) along the time on stream is mainly due to the decrease of the heavy components (GC-MS non-detected fraction), whereas just minor changes are observed in the yield of the light species (GC-MS detected fraction), as illustrated in Figure 8-a, b. This relevant result indicates that the biochar catalytic activity is mainly denoted on heavy/oligomeric species provoking their transformation into the other fractions: gases, GC-MS detected components, and even into additional biochar.

Considering the time evolution at 550 °C, the yields of AC, KET & ETH and FUR tend to decrease, showing that these components are also affected in great extension by cracking and deoxygenation reactions catalysed by biochar. In contrast, the yield of O-AR remains quite stable while that of SUG is augmented during the first three hours, then declining slightly in the last one. These findings evidence that, for these two families, their possible transformation through different routes is compensated by the conversion of oligomers present in the GC-MS non-detected fraction into levoglucosan and small O-AR compounds.

Figure 7. Time evolution of bio-oil* component yields, grouped by families, at different pyrolysis temperatures: 300 (a), 450 (b) and 550 °C (c).

Figure 8. Yield of the bio-oil* GC-MS detected (a) and non-detected (b) fraction as a function of time on stream for experiments performed at 300, 450 and 550 °C.

In order to assess the effect of the temperature on the molecular composition of the bio-oil*, Figure 9 shows the cumulative yields of the different families detected by GC-MS. Moreover, Table S1 summarizes the overall yield obtained for the most abundant components in each family at three pyrolysis temperatures (300, 450, and 550 °C). In most cases, a maximum is observed, which occurs at different temperatures depending on the family: ketones & ethers at 300 °C, furans and acids at 400 °C, oxygenated aromatics at 450 °C and sugars at 500 °C. This finding is consistent with most of these components being intermediate products in the pyrolysis process sequence since, at high temperatures, they are transformed into non-condensable gases [48,49], or tend to re-polymerize [50]. In the case of the AC family (Table S1), the three most abundant compounds (acetic, propanoic, and butanoic acids) present a maximum yield at the intermediate temperature (450 °C). The same occurs for furfural and levoglucosan, which are the components showing the highest yield within the FUR and SUG families, respectively. However, these trends do not apply to other species as it can be observed for the individual

components of the KET & ETH family. This can be explained by the high degree of oxygen functionality in many of these compounds that favour the occurrence of a great variety of reactions, being influenced differently by the temperature and catalytic biochar effects.

Figure 9. Cumulative yields of bio-oil* components, grouped by families, as a function of pyrolysis temperature.

On the other hand, not only a decrease in the overall yield of oxygenated aromatic compounds is observed but also changes in the distribution of phenolic sub-families occur at the highest temperature of 550 °C (Figure S4, Table S1). Whereas phenyl ketones have not a clear tendency, showing a maximum along the time on stream, both guaiacols and syringols are progressively consumed, which can be linked with the enhanced production of O-AR components with lower oxygen functionalities, like catechol, phenol and cresol. As shown in Table S1, these changes are more pronounced when increasing the pyrolysis temperature, which can be assigned to the enhanced catalytic effect of the biochar. A simple reaction scheme summarizing these transformations is illustrated in Figure 10, being also congruent with previous works [51–53]. Cracking of the raw lignin or lignin oligomers produces a number of components with a relatively high degree of oxygen functionalization (syringols, guaiacols and phenyl ketones). Subsequently,

these compounds undergo demethoxylation, demethylation and deacetylation reactions, leading to the formation of light phenolic derivatives (catechol, phenol and cresol).

Figure 10. Reaction scheme of the transformations involving selected O-AR components during pyrolysis.

3.5. Effects of biochar as external catalyst

In this section, further insights into the catalytic role of the two major biochar components (carbonaceous matter and AAEMs) during oak wood pyrolysis are provided by using two biochar samples as external catalysts. These materials consisted of the biochar produced in the test performed at 500 °C (biochar-raw) and this same sample after modification by impregnation with 5 wt% potassium (biochar-K). The catalytic tests were performed operating the continuous reaction system at different temperatures in the thermal and catalytic zones. A relatively low temperature (400 °C) was set in the upper zone to ensure minimum interferences in the product distribution by the additional biochar produced in the test. For the same reason, the products being assessed were those generated just during the first hour of time on stream. On the other hand, a high temperature (500 °C) was selected for the catalytic zone to maximize the effects derived from the behaviour of the external biochar as a catalyst.

Figures S5-a and b depict the results obtained in these tests in terms of fraction yields and bio-oil* elemental composition, respectively, using as reference those corresponding to the experiment performed at 400 °C without any external catalyst. These figures confirm the relevant catalytic role of the biochar samples, leading to a sharp decline in the bio-oil* yield and an increase in the gas production. Moreover, it can be observed that both biochar materials behave in a very different way, with the biochar-K sample inducing stronger changes in the product distribution in comparison with the reference test as a consequence of the catalytic properties of the incorporated K species. Thus, biochar-K leads to a strong reduction of the bio-oil* yield, producing also additional coke that is deposited over the catalyst itself, while decreasing significantly the bio-oil* oxygen content (from 37.7 to 19.0 wt%). In contrast, the biochar-raw just decreases slightly the oxygen concentration (34.6 wt%) of the organic liquid fraction.

Important differences can be also denoted between both biochars in terms of deoxygenation pathways. As shown in Figures S5-a and c, the biochar-raw enhances the production of H₂O, CO and CO₂, while the biochar-K has mainly a strong effect on the CO₂ generation. Accordingly, it can be envisaged that the carbonaceous matrix in the biochar promotes preferentially dehydration and decarbonylation reactions, whereas the K species seem to favour rather the occurrence of the decarboxylation route.

As illustrated in Figure 11, the bio-oil* composition undergoes also relevant changes when the biochar samples are incorporated as external catalysts. Thus, both biochar catalysts provoke a significant reduction in the yield of heavy/oligomeric species (GC-MS non-detected components), being this effect quite more pronounced on the K-impregnated material. In contrast, the overall yield of light species in the bio-oil* is little affected by the biochar catalysts, probably due to a compensating effect between the occurrence of depolymerization transformations of the heavier components and cracking/deoxygenation into gases. These

results suggest that both carbonaceous matter and AAEMs contribute to the removal of heavy/oligomeric species. In this way, it can be envisaged that they are preferentially retained by adsorption on the carbonaceous matter of the biochar, facilitating their subsequent transformation catalysed by the AAEMs species.

On the other hand, sharp variations can be also appreciated in the share of the different compound families. In general, the biochar-raw catalyst affects negatively the yield of most families, except for SUG and KET & ETH (Figure 11.b). Likewise, the biochar-K material provokes the almost total disappearance of AC, FUR and SUG, which can be linked with the great extension of decarboxylation reactions that occur over this sample as above commented. However, it also causes an enhancement in the production of KET & ETH and O-AR. In particular, the number of cyclic ketones, identified in the GC-MS analyses, and their yield increase significantly over the biochar-K catalyst. This result suggests that a significant fraction of FUR and SUG are converted to cyclic ketones, mainly cyclopentenone, as reported also by previous works using activated carbons and K-modified zeolites as catalysts [54,55]. As illustrated in Figure 11.c, for the O-AR sub-families, the K-impregnated biochar promotes mainly the formation of cresol and phenol. In this way, Zhang et al. report that these phenolic components can be produced not just from the lignin component of biomass, but also from cellulose with cyclic ketones acting as intermediates in the reaction pathway proposed [56]. This fact is in good agreement with the enhanced production of both cyclic ketones and cresol observed in Figure 11.c, when using the biochar-K catalyst.

Figure 11. Yields obtained in the pyrolysis tests using biochars as external catalysts: GC-MS detected and non-detected component (a), compounds families (b) and O-AR sub-families.

Finally, it must be pointed out that the molecular composition of the bio-oils* produced over the biochar catalysts agrees well with their oxygen content. Thus, the organic liquid fraction obtained over the biochar-raw sample is rich in highly functionalized species (like AC, SUG, and

FUR), explaining that its oxygen content is just slightly lower than that of the bio-oil* corresponding to the reference test. In contrast, the bio-oil* generated over the biochar-K catalyst contains mainly simple phenolic compounds (phenol and cresol), being in good agreement with its relatively low oxygen concentration.

4. Conclusions

The use of a continuous reaction system to investigate the pyrolysis of a lignocellulosic biomass (oak woodchips) has allowed assessing, under in situ conditions, the autocatalytic properties of the biochar fraction and their dependence on the pyrolysis temperature.

For the tests performed at the lowest temperatures (300 and 350 °C), the operation of the system is close to steady-state with almost no changes being observed in the product distribution along the reaction time. In contrast, a remarkable variation in the yields and compositions of the pyrolysis products with the reaction time was observed when operating at higher temperatures, which has been assigned to autocatalytic effects originated by the biochar that is progressively accumulated within the reactor. Thus, the bio-oil* yield was gradually reduced along the time on stream due to a higher production of gases and, in particular, of CO₂ and CO. This fact agrees well with the reduction of the bio-oil* oxygen concentration that occurs at long times on stream, in particular for the highest pyrolysis temperatures (500 and 550 °C).

The catalytic activity of the biochar also influences the bio-oil molecular composition at temperatures above 400 °C. In particular, a strong decline in the yield of heavy and oligomeric components takes place along the time on stream. Likewise, the time evolution of light species in the bio-oil* undergoes significant changes, decreasing the acetic acid production but augmenting that of several oxygenated aromatics. A more complex trend is observed in the case of sugars, whose yield presents a maximum at 550 °C along the time on stream.

The origin of the biochar autocatalytic properties can be linked in principle to its relatively high AAEMs content, although the possible contribution of the carbonaceous matter cannot be

neglected. In this way, additional pyrolysis tests, performed using biochars with different K content as external catalysts, indicate that this inorganic component is highly active for catalysing decarboxylation reactions. As a consequence, a highly deoxygenated bio-oil* is produced having a large concentration of simple phenolics compounds and almost free of carboxylic acids, sugars and furans. In any case, both raw and K-loaded biochar samples present a high catalytic activity in the conversion of heavy/oligomeric species into light compounds and gases. This indicates that the contribution of the carbonaceous matrix is key to promote depolymerization reactions, interacting synergistically with the AAEMs species.

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